

Appendix 2: Illustrated Guide to Galls and Leaf Mines of Nantucket and Tuckernuck Draft, February 2021

Representative photographs of the galls and leaf mines found on Nantucket and Tuckernuck by Charley Eiseman, Julia Blyth, Noah Charney, and Sydne Record are presented here. They are arranged by host plant, with the plant families presented alphabetically. Each short description is followed by the reference used to make the identification and the initials of the photographer (CSE = Charley Eiseman; JAB = Julia Blyth; NDC = Noah Charney). Additional species listed by Johnson (1930) and Jones and Kimball (1943) are incorporated, with updated taxonomy.

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ADOXACEAE

Viburnum dentatum (Arrowwood)

Blisters in viburnum leaves are caused by *Sackenomyia commota* (Cecidomyiidae). (Gagné 1989; CSE)

Elongate reddish galls between arrowwood leaf veins are caused by an unidentified mite, referred to by Felt (1940) as “*Eriophyes* sp.” (Eriophyidae). These galls are fuzzy on the underside, unlike the midge galls above. In the lower left corner of this photo is an “upside-down” mite gall, with the fuzz (erineum) on the upper leaf surface. (CSE)

We reared *Phyllonorycter viburnella* (Gracillariidae) from these underside tentiform mines in arrowwood leaves. According to Maier & Davis (1989), this species is usually scarce even where its food plant abounds. (CSE)

This long, winding mine is the work of *Marmara viburnella* (Gracillariidae), a species recently described from three adults reared from cocoons collected on Nantucket. The mine disappears into the petiole,

from which the larva burrows down the stem. The larva continues to mine in the stem until the following spring, when it cuts a semicircular flap in the bark and spins its cocoon under this. Adults emerge in late June and early July. (CSE)

AMARANTHACEAE

Atriplex (Orache)

Moth larvae were found mining leaves of orache at Madaket Marine in mid-June. Within a few days of being collected, they transitioned to feeding externally. The adult that emerged was identified by Terry Harrison as *Scrobipalpa* **nr. atriplicella** (Gelechiidae). (CSE)

Chenopodium (Lambsquarters)

Chrysoesthia sexguttella (Gelechiidae) makes distinctive white blotch mines, with the black excrement concentrated near the beginning, on lambsquarters leaves. (Eiseman & Charney 2010; CSE)

Salicornia (Glasswort)

We reared *Erynephala maritima* (Chrysomelidae) from larvae found mining stems of glasswort at Masquetuck (CSE).

ANACARDIACEAE

Rhus glabra (Smooth Sumac), *Rhus typhina* (Staghorn Sumac)

Contorted, narrow, linear mines in sumac leaves are the work of *Stigmella intermedia* (Nepticulidae). (Newton & Wilkinson 1982; NDC)

Caloptilia rhoifoliella (Gracillariidae) starts out as a leafminer, making a white mine that is at first linear, later widening into a blotch (which may not be connected to the linear portion). Finally, the larva exits the mine and rolls the leaf downward from the tip, finishing its feeding within this roll. (CSE)

Toxicodendron radicans (Poison Ivy), *T. vernix* (Poison Sumac)

Aculops rhois (Eriophyidae) causes warty galls on poison ivy and poison sumac leaves. (Eiseman & Charney 2010; CSE)

The linear mine in this poison ivy leaf (left) was made by a *Stigmella rhoifoliella* larva (Nepticulidae), and the blotch mines (right) contain larvae of *Cameraria guttifinitella* (Gracillariidae). (Eiseman & Charney 2010; NDC)

Caloptilia rhoifoliella (Gracillariidae) starts out as a leafminer, making a white mine that is at first linear, later widening into a blotch (which may not be connected to the linear portion). Finally, the larva exits the mine and rolls the leaf downward from the tip, finishing its feeding within this roll. (Chambers 1876; JAB, CSE)

APIACEAE

Heracleum maximum (Cow Parsnip)

More than one agromyzid is known to make linear mines in cow parsnip leaves, but we reared an adult from these mines, which Owen Lonsdale identified as *Phytomyza spondylii*. He noted that this is a new state record, the previous records being from Quebec, Alberta, California, and Oregon. (JAB)

APOCYNACEAE

Asclepias syriaca (Common Milkweed)

Blotch mines on the upper surface of milkweed leaves are the work of *Liriomyza asclepiadis* (Agromyzidae). (Eiseman & Charney 2010; NDC)

AQUIFOLIACEAE

Ilex glabra (Inkberry)

Phytomyza glabricola (Agromyzidae) is the only known leaf-mining fly on inkberry. (Lonsdale & Scheffer 2011; CSE)

Ilex opaca (American Holly)

Phytomyza ilicicola (Agromyzidae) makes linear-blotch mines in evergreen holly leaves. (Lonsdale & Scheffer 2011; CSE)

Ilex verticillata (Winterberry)

Four different *Phytomyza* species (Agromyzidae) form twisting linear mines on winterberry leaves: *P. ditmani*, *P. lineata*, *P. verticillatae*, and *P. wiggii*. The adults we reared in 2013 were identified as *Phytomyza wiggii*. (Lonsdale & Scheffer 2011; CSE)

The larvae of *Rhopobota dietziana* and *R. finitimana* (Tortricidae) start out as leafminers in winterberry leaves, pushing their excrement out the bottom of the mine in a distinctive curved stick, and then exit to complete their development as leafrollers/tiers. (Eiseman 2014; CSE)

ARALIACEAE

Hydrocotyle (Water Pennywort)

We are unsure what causes these bumps on water pennywort leaves, but we suspect a fungus (CSE).

ASPARAGACEAE

Asparagus officinalis (Asparagus)

Johnson (1930) lists *Agromyza maura* var. *simplex* (Agromyzidae), now known as *Ophiomyia simplex*. The larva is a miner in asparagus stems. (Spencer & Steyskal 1986)

ASPHODELACEAE

Hemerocallis (Daylily)

Ophiomyia kwansonis (Agromyzidae), only recently confirmed in North America, makes long, white, linear mines in daylily leaves. (Steck & Williams 2012; CSE)

ASTERACEAE

Arctium (Burdock)

Narrow, white, linear mines on burdock leaves are made by *Phytomyza syngenesiae* (Agromyzidae). (CSE)

Baccharis halimifolia (Groundsel)

Bucculatrix ivella mines a short linear track with a conspicuous line of black frass within it, then emerges to feed externally. It feeds on either the upper or lower side of the leaf, forming small, irregular patches that leave the epidermis on the other side of the leaf intact. (Braun 1963; CSE)

These mines are much longer than those of *Bucculatrix ivella* and are clearly the work of an agromyzid, but no agromyzid is known to produce long, linear mines in groundsel. (CSE)

The distinct spiral at the beginning of these mines identifies them as the work of *Liriomyza eupatorii* (Agromyzidae), which has not previously been recorded from *Baccharis*. (Eiseman & Lonsdale 2018; CSE)

We reared *Nemorimyza posticata* (Agromyzidae) from these mines, which start out linear and gradually widen to an irregular blotch. They are typically at the edge of the leaf as shown here. The conspicuous feeding lines described by Spencer & Steyskal (1986) for this species are not evident on this host plant. *N. maculosa* (see below) is also recorded from groundsel but we did not find its mines on this host. (CSE)

Bidens (Beggar-ticks)

We suspect this irregular stem gall (left) is caused by a fungus or other pathogen. From this stem emerged a moth (Tortricidae: *Epiblema otiosana*), two shining flower beetles (Phalacridae, tentatively identified as *Stilbus apicalis*), three minute brown scavenger beetles (Latridiidae: Corticariinae), and a number of frit flies (Chloropidae: *Elachiptera*). The moth's pupa was in a slight, frass-filled swelling in the stem (below), well below the gall that had caught our attention. (CSE)

This linear beggar-ticks leaf mine was made by *Phytomyza syngenesiae* (Agromyzidae). (CSE)

Calycomyza platyptera (Agromyzidae) forms digitate blotch mines on leaves of beggar-ticks and other Asteraceae (CSE).

An unknown insect formed a spiral gallery in this *Bidens connata* petiole, causing the leaf to droop. A few weeks later a moth larva emerged from a hole in the stem, but it is unclear whether it was the maker of the petiole mine and we were unable to rear it (CSE).

Cirsium horridulum (Yellow Thistle)

We reared adults of *Oulema palustris* (Chrysomelidae) from these larvae forming linear mines in yellow thistle leaves. (CSE)

Erechtites hieraciifolius (Pilewort)

An undescribed species of *Neolasioptera* (Cecidomyiidae) causes swellings in pilewort stems. We reared an adult midge from this gall as well as a Torymid wasp. (Gagné 1989; CSE)

Nemorimyza maculosa (Agromyzidae) forms large blotch mines on leaves of pilewort and other members of the aster family, often with multiple larvae in a single mine. (Spencer & Steyskal 1986; CSE)

Phyllocnistis insignis (Gracillariidae) forms a long, narrow, linear mine, spinning its cocoon at the end (CSE).

The white puparium found on the leaf underside at the end of this mine indicates a *Phytomyza* species (Agromyzidae), but none has yet been recorded from *Erechtites*. It is almost certainly *P. syngenesiae*, which feeds on a wide variety of Asteraceae. (CSE)

This shorter linear mine was apparently made by a *Liriomyza* larva (Agromyzidae), which exited before pupating (CSE).

Erigeron (Fleabane, Horseweed)

Linear mines on fleabane are made by species in the *Phytomyza albiceps* species group (Agromyzidae). (CSE)

We reared *Nemorimyza maculosa* (Agromyzidae) from this brown blotch mine at the tip of a horseweed leaf. (CSE)

Eurybia divaricata (White Wood Aster)

An unknown species in the *Phytomyza albiceps* group (Agromyzidae) forms linear mines in leaves of white wood aster (CSE).

Euthamia (Slender Goldenrod, Grass-leaved Goldenrod)

Stalkless galls with longitudinal ribbing, found on various parts of the plant, are caused by *Rhopalomyia fusiformae* (Cecidomyiidae). *R. pedicellata* galls, which we did not find on Nantucket, are identical except each one sits on a pedicel that is about as long as the remainder of the gall. (Gagné 1989; CSE)

Asteromyia euthamiae (Cecidomyiidae) causes black blisters on leaves of grass-leaved goldenrod with a symbiotic fungus inside. (Gagné 1989; CSE)

This gall of *Rhopalomyia lobata* (Cecidomyiidae) also has a symbiotic fungus lining the larval cell (Dorchin et al. 2009; CSE).

This rosette gall on slender goldenrod is probably caused by another gall midge (*Cecidomyiidae*) (CSE).

We suspect this leaf mine is the work of *Liriomyza eupatorii* (Agromyzidae), but so far we have not had an opportunity to rear adults. (CSE)

This longer, narrower mine, with the puparium formed internally, is made by an *Ophiomyia* species (Agromyzidae). It is likely *O. maura* rather than *O. euthamiae*, based on the bluish puparium and its being entirely on the lower surface (Eiseman & Lonsdale 2018; CSE).

Whitish blotch mines on grass-leaved goldenrod are formed by a species of *Calycomyza* (Agromyzidae). So far we have only been able to rear an unidentifiable female (Eiseman & Lonsdale 2018; CSE).

Hieracium (Hawkweed)

The lack of visible frass grains in this leaf mine suggests that it was made from a different **agromyzid** than the other unidentified mines we found in members of the aster family. (CSE)

Ionactis linariifolius (Flax-leaved Aster)

We reared a species of *Dasineura* (Cecidomyiidae) from this gall at the top of a flax-leaved aster plant (CSE).

Iva frutescens (Marsh Elder)

A species of *Marmara* (Gracillariidae) forms a linear mine on marsh elder leaves, descending through the petiole into the stem. Here, it feeds until the following spring, without leaving any external evidence. Unlike *M. viburnella*, which otherwise has similar habits (on arrowwood), the larva exits the stem before spinning its cocoon (CSE).

This much wider linear mine is probably made by a species of *Liriomyza* (Agromyzidae) (CSE).

We reared *Calycomyza platyptera* (Agromyzidae) from digitate blotch mines on marsh elder (Eiseman & Lonsdale 2018). Johnson (1930) listed *C. platyptera* as *Agromyza platyptera* var. *jucunda*. Other recorded hosts of this fly include *Ambrosia*, *Arctium*, *Artemisia*, *Aster*, *Baccharis*, *Bidens*, *Erigeron*, *Gnaphalium*, *Helianthus*, *Solidago*, *Xanthium*, and *Zinnia*. The puparium is attached to a pile of frass at the center of the completed mine (CSE).

This midge was found dead in a bag in which we had placed an uprooted marsh elder plant to rear the *Marmara* species discussed above. Raymond J. Gagné identified it as a species of *Neolasioptera* (Cecidomyiidae) that has been reared from stem galls in Florida (CSE).

Leucanthemum vulgare (Oxeye Daisy)

We reared *Phytomyza syngenesiae* (Agromyzidae) from these linear mines on oxeye daisy. (JAB)

Mikania scandens (Climbing Hempvine)

Neolasioptera perfoliata (Cecidomyiidae) forms galls in stems of climbing hempvine (CSE).

Leaf mines of *Leucospilapteryx venustella* (Gracillariidae) start out as a long, narrow, epidermal track on the lower surface, then expand to a tentiform blotch (CSE).

Mines of *Liriomyza carphephori* (Agromyzidae) often start out at the tip of the leaf, where they are very contorted, as in this example. Mines that start away from the leaf tip often undulate between the upper and lower leaf surfaces (CSE).

Nabalus trifoliolatus (Three-leaved Rattlesnake-root)

This leaf mine was already empty on June 12. By rearing adults from similar mines elsewhere in New England, we have determined that they are made by *Ophiomyia congregata* (Agromyzidae), which feeds in the fall and again in early spring before pupating in the petiole (CSE).

This aborted stem mine was probably made by a different species of *Ophiomyia* (Agromyzidae) (CSE).

Based on the known leafminers of *Nabalus*, this elongate blotch is likely the work of *Liriomyza orilliensis* (Agromyzidae) (CSE).

Pseudognaphalium obtusifolium (Sweet Everlasting)

An unknown species of *Liriomyza* (Agromyzidae) forms linear mines in leaves of sweet everlasting (CSE).

Solidago (Goldenrod)

This gall is superficially similar to the spherical stem gall of *Eurosta solidaginis* (Tephritidae), which we did not find on Nantucket, but was listed by Johnson (1930, as *E. asteri*). *Gnorimoschema* larvae (Gelechiidae) also develop in swellings in goldenrod stems. In June, the larva chews an exit hole near the top of the gall, then plugs it with excrement; the adult moth emerges through this hole in late summer. The presence of this plugged hole distinguishes these galls from goldenrod stem swellings caused by *E. solidaginis* and other insects (Miller 1963). Each *Gnorimoschema* species develops in a different species of goldenrod, and apparently none has been recorded using Elliott's goldenrod (*S. latissimifolia*), so it is unclear which species is responsible for these galls. Jones and Kimball (1943) reported galls of *G. salinaris* as fairly common in seaside goldenrod (*S. sempervirens*). (CSE)

The other goldenrod-galling fruit fly (Tephritidae) listed by Johnson (1930) was *Procecidochares polita*, which causes small rosette galls (Felt 1940). Netta Dorchin confirmed that the galls at left, on rough-stemmed goldenrod, were caused by a *Procecidochares*, but we are not sure which species. (CSE)

This terminal rosette gall is the first of its kind documented on seaside goldenrod. It is caused by a species of *Asphondylia* (Cecidomyiidae). The cells containing the larvae were lined with a white symbiotic fungus. The adult midges that emerged from it, and from similar galls Charley Eiseman found in Maine, were sent to Netta Dorchin for examination and DNA analysis. She reported: “This is most probably a new species but the molecular data were unable to separate it from a population I have from *Solidago bicolor* [silverrod] from Virginia. The two populations are mixed together and I won’t be able to understand what’s going on there and how many species are involved until I have bigger samples from both host plants for molecular study.” (Dorchin et al. 2015; NDC)

This rosette gall on rough-stemmed goldenrod is caused by *Asphondylia rosulata* (Cecidomyiidae) (Dorchin et al. 2015; CSE).

This single-celled gall on Elliott's goldenrod is caused by yet another *Asphondylia* species (Cecidomyiidae). None has previously been recorded from this host. (CSE)

We found several of these small, elongate rosette galls on branches of rough-stemmed goldenrod. They are probably caused by a gall midge (Cecidomyiidae), but it is unclear what species it would be. A single midge larva emerged from one of the galls on August 10, but this was probably a predator or inquiline rather than the gallmaker. (CSE)

These distorted leaves on Elliott's goldenrod represent another unidentified gallmaker, again probably a gall midge (Cecidomyiidae). Parasitoid wasps emerged from this gall after we collected it. Netta Dorchin said it somewhat resembles galls she has collected on blue-stemmed goldenrod (*S. caesia*), caused by an undescribed species of *Asphondylia*. (CSE)

The most similar known galls to these modified Elliott's Goldenrod florets are caused by midges in the genus *Rhopalomyia* (Cecidomyiidae), but none are exactly like this and none are recorded from this particular goldenrod species. (Gagné 1989; CSE)

This small leaf gall on Elliott's goldenrod is either caused by *Rhopalomyia clarkei* (Cecidomyiidae) or a closely related, undescribed species. (Gagné 1989; CSE)

On goldenrod leaves, *Asteromyia carbonifera* (Cecidomyiidae) forms flat, circular galls containing a hard, black symbiotic fungus. (Eiseman & Charney 2010; CSE)

A closely related species to the above, *Asteromyia modesta* (Cecidomyiidae) develops in inconspicuous leaf spots without an obvious fungal lining. We did not notice this gall in the field, but discovered it when looking for the source of the adult midge that appeared in a vial containing leaves with mines of *Calycomyza solidaginis*. The white object projecting from the gall is the pupal skin. (Gagné 1989; CSE)

The blotch mine of *Microrhopala vittata* (Chrysomelidae) on goldenrod can be recognized by the excrement-covered eggs deposited on the lower leaf surface (CSE).

Cremastobombycia solidaginis (Gracillariidae) makes an elongate, wrinkled mine on the underside of a goldenrod leaf. We reared an adult from rough-stemmed goldenrod, and found mines on two other goldenrod species. (De Prins & De Prins 2010; CSE)

We reared *Nemorimyza posticata* (Agromyzidae) from this blotch mine at the tip of a tall goldenrod leaf. A more elongate blotch mine found along the edge of a nearby leaf is presumed to be the work of the same species. (CSE)

We reared *Calycomyza solidaginis* (Agromyzidae) from this and other, similar whitish linear-blotch mines on goldenrod leaves (the linear portion is sometimes obscured). The larva pupates within the mine, as shown here. (CSE)

We reared adults of *Phytomyza astotinensis* (Agromyzidae), a species previously confirmed only from western Canada, from linear mines like this one on Elliott's goldenrod (CSE).

The spiral at the beginning of this mine indicates that it was made by *Liriomyza eupatorii* (Agromyzidae). (Spencer & Steyskal 1986; CSE)

This distinctive mine differs from the previous two linear agromyzid fly mines in being extremely narrow throughout its length, and in having the puparium hidden in a blister on the leaf underside (the other species exit the mine to pupate on the ground). We have determined that it is made by *Ophiomyia maura*. (CSE)

Sonchus asper (Spiny Sowthistle)

Sowthistle is a favorite host of *Phytomyza syngenesiae* (Agromyzidae) (CSE).

Symphotrichum (Aster)

These fuzzy galls on bushy aster are caused by an undetermined species of *Rhopalomyia* (Cecidomyiidae) (CSE).

This *Asteromyia* (Cecidomyiidae) adult emerged from an unseen gall in a vial containing the *Rhopalomyia* galls pictured above. *Asteromyia* species form spot or blister galls that are sometimes difficult to detect (CSE).

The characteristic spiral at the beginning of this mine indicates that it was made by *Liriomyza eupatorii* (Agromyzidae). (Spencer & Steyskal 1986; CSE)

Ophiomyia parda (Agromyzidae) forms a distinctive linear mine with frass in widely spaced lumps (CSE).

The leaf mine of *Ophiomyia carolinensis* (Agromyzidae) begins as an intermittent linear track and ends as an elongate blotch along both sides of the midrib (CSE).

Calycomyza promissa (Agromyzidae) forms linear-blotch mines on aster leaves. The puparium is formed on a characteristic pedestal of frass attached to the floor of the mine (CSE).

This blotch mine contains a larva of *Sumitrosis inaequalis* (Chrysomelidae), listed by Johnson (1930) as *Anoplitis inaequalis* (CSE).

Tanacetum parthenium (Feverfew)

Mines of *Phytomyza syngenesiae* (Agromyzidae) are common on the feverfew in the garden outside the Maria Mitchell Association museum. (JAB)

Taraxacum officinale (Dandelion)

We reared an as yet undetermined species of *Ophiomyia* (Agromyzidae) from this branching mine in a dandelion leaf. The puparium was formed in another leaf in the rosette, hidden on the lower surface (CSE).

BALSAMINACEAE

Impatiens capensis (Jewelweed)

Phytoliriomyza melampyga (Agromyzidae), listed by Johnson (1930) as *Agromyza melampyga*, makes linear-blotch mines in jewelweed leaves. (Eiseman & Charney 2010; CSE)

BETULACEAE

Betula populifolia (Gray Birch)

Both times we encountered gray birch on Nantucket, the introduced leaf-mining sawfly *Fenusa pumila* (Tenthredinidae) was present (CSE).

Several species of *Parornix* (Gracillariidae) feed on birch, first in an underside tentiform mine and later in a folded-down leaf edge (CSE).

We found an undetermined species of *Stigmella* (Nepticulidae) on gray birch at Wigwam Ponds (CSE).

Corylus (Hazelnut)

Deformed hazelnut catkins like these have been attributed to “*Cecidomyia squamulicola*” (Cecidomyiidae), but the larvae and adults have never been described, so it is not known what the proper generic placement is. (Gagné 1989; CSE)

The enlarged bud at left, found in September, is a midge gall (**Cecidomyiidae**). Larvae of undescribed *Contarinia* and *Dasineura* species have been collected from galls like this. (Gagné 1989; CSE)

This gall is a good match for the original description of *Eriophyes coryli* (Eriophyidae): “A deformity of the leaf brought about by the excessive

shortening and thickening of midrib and some of the main veins, producing puckering of the blade tissues. The thickened sac-like veins are really the galls, opening by slits above. Pubescent.” It is not clear what the currently accepted name for this species is, if in fact the mites themselves have ever been described. (Stebbins 1909; CSE)

These hazelnut leaf blisters are a mystery to us. Our impression in the field was that they were caused by eriophyid mites, and it is possible that they simply represent a less severe infestation of “*Eriophyes coryli*” than the one in the previous example.

This bark mine on American hazelnut is presumably the work of a *Marmara* larva (Gracillariidae), but no species is known to use this host. (CSE)

We found several *Brachys* (Buprestidae) mines on American and beaked hazelnuts, identifiable by the conspicuous, shining eggshell on the upper surface (CSE).

Cameraria corylisella (Gracillariidae) produces a nearly circular, brownish yellow blotch mine on the upper sides of hazelnut, musclewood, and hophornbeam leaves. We also found a roughly rectangular mine on hazelnut, confined by two lateral veins, which we presume to have been made by this species. (De Prins & De Prins 2010; NDC)

Phyllonorycter intermixta (Gracillariidae) forms underside tentiform mines in hazelnut leaves. This particular mine was parasitized by a bethylid wasp. (Braun 1930; CSE)

The mine of *Orchestes mixtus* (Curculionidae) begins at the midrib and is initially linear, eventually becoming a puffy blotch at the tip of the leaf. This species has previously been reported from *Corylus cornuta*, but *C. americana* is a new host record (Anderson 1989). (CSE)

Stigmella corylifoliella (Nepticulidae) produces a narrow mine with a continuous frass line in hazelnut leaves. The larva is yellow. (Eiseman & Charney 2010; NDC)

Ectoedemia quadrinotata (Nepticulidae) also forms a linear mine on hazelnut, but it starts out very narrow and widens abruptly (and may become somewhat blotchy), with frass scattered at random. The larva is transparent except for its green gut contents and a central line of tiny black dots (CSE).

Ectoedemia virgulae (Nepticulidae) also makes broadly linear mines with scattered frass, but unlike *E. quadrinotata* there is not a narrow beginning and the larva is distinctly green (CSE).

Much smaller linear mines are made by larvae of *Bucculatrix* (Bucculatricidae), which complete their development as external feeders on the lower leaf surface. Two species are known to feed on hazelnut, and we have not determined which of these is on Nantucket (CSE).

BIGNONIACEAE

Catalpa (Catalpa)

Amauromyza pleuralis (Agromyzidae) forms linear-blotch mines in catalpa leaves (CSE).

BLECHNACEAE

Woodwardia areolata (Netted Chain Fern)

We reared *Chirosia gleniensis* (Anthomyiidae) from mines in pinnae of netted chain fern. This species was previously only known to feed on sensitive fern (Eiseman 2018; CSE).

BRASSICACEAE

In addition to *Phyllotreta chalybeipennis* (below), Johnson (1930) listed *P. sinuata*, which chiefly mines the leaves of pepper grass (*Lepidium* spp.) according to Needham et al. (1928). However, Smith (1985) considered *P. sinuata* a synonym of *P. striolata*, which is a root feeder rather than a leafminer. Clark et al. (2004) list a number of *Phyllotreta* species that feed on *Lepidium* spp. *Plutella xylostella* (Plutellidae), listed by Jones & Kimball (1943) as *P. maculipennis*, feeds on garden *Brassica* spp. and other mustards, forming tiny leaf mines in the first instar and later feeding externally.

Cakile edentula (Sea Rocket)

Phyllotreta chalybeipennis (Chrysomelidae) forms irregular mines in sea rocket leaves. This species was listed by Johnson (1930). (CSE)

Liriomyza brassicae (Agromyzidae) forms linear mines in leaves of sea rocket, among many other plants. This is probably the species Johnson (1930) referred to as *Agromyza pusilla* (Agromyzidae), the “serpentine leafminer.” (CSE)

BUXACEAE

Buxus (Boxwood)

Monarthropalpus flavus (Cecidomyiidae), the so-called “boxwood leafminer,” forms blisterlike galls on boxwood leaves. When the adult midge emerges, the pupal exuviae are left protruding from the gall (CSE).

CAPRIFOLIACEAE

Lonicera (Honeysuckle)

Aulagromyza cornigera (Agromyzidae) mines honeysuckle leaves in the spring, depositing frass in characteristic discrete, widely spaced grains. (CSE)

We reared *Aulagromyza luteoscutellata* (Agromyzidae) from these linear mines in Morrow's honeysuckle leaves. (CSE)

Perittia herrichiella (Elachistidae) makes a full-depth blotch mine at the edges of honeysuckle leaves. The only published North American record for this introduced European species is from Quebec (Kaila 1995). (CSE)

Several species of *Phyllonorycter* (Gracillariidae) form underside tentiform mines on honeysuckle leaves. (CSE)

CARYOPHYLLACEAE

Saponaria officinalis (Bouncing Bet)

Amauromyza flavifrons (Agromyzidae) makes white linear-blotch mines in bouncing bet leaves. The linear portion is sometimes obliterated by the blotch, as has happened here. (Spencer & Steyskal 1986; CSE)

CISTACEAE

Crocanthemum (frostweed, rockrose)

An undescribed species of *Mompha* (Momphidae) mines leaves of frostweed and rockrose, then exits and spins its cocoon between tied leaves. (CSE)

CONVOLVULACEAE

Calystegia (Bindweed)

Young larvae of *Bedellia somnulentella* (Bedelliidae) form linear mines. Older larvae form full-depth blotch mines, expelling all of their frass through holes in the lower epidermis (CSE).

Neolasioptera convolvuli
(Cecidomyiidae) forms galls in
bindweed stems (CSE).

CORNACEAE

Cornus (Dogwood)

Resseliella clavula (Cecidomyiidae), listed by Johnson (1930)
as *Lasioptera clavula*, causes a smooth, clublike enlargement
just below the bud in apical branches of flowering dogwood
(Gagné 1989) (CSE).

Parallelodiplosis subtruncata (Cecidomyiidae)
forms circular spot or blister galls in dogwood
leaves (CSE).

CUPRESSACEAE

Juniperus virginiana (Eastern Red Cedar)

This bizarre orange and purple growth on red cedar is caused by a fungus, *Gymnosporangium juniperi-virginianae* (Pucciniaceae), which also causes rust on apple leaves (JAB).

Thuja occidentalis (Arborvitae)

Several species of *Argyresthia* (Argyresthiidae) and *Coleotechnites* (Gelechiidae) are leafminers of arborvitae (CSE).

CYPERACEAE

Bolboschoenus robustus (Sturdy Bulrush)

An unknown *Acalyptris* species (Nepticulidae) forms linear mines on the undersides of sturdy bulrush leaves (CSE).

Carex crinita (Fringed Sedge), *C. lurida* (Sallow Sedge), *C. swanii* (Swan's Sedge)

Several species of *Cerodontha* (Agromyzidae) produce whitish mines on sedge

leaves that are visible on just one leaf surface, with very little frass. We reared *C. angulata* from this mine on Fringed Sedge (Eiseman & Lonsdale 2018; CSE).

These mines on Swan's Sedge, with the pale brown puparium formed inside, are likely the work of *C. morosa* (CSE).

Scirpus (Bulrush)

A species of *Monochroa* (Gelechiidae) mines in bulrush leaves, expelling frass from a hole at one end of the mine (CSE).

This is a very young mine made by four *Cerodontha* (Agromyzidae) larvae feeding side by side. The species is probably *C. scirpivora*, which has only been confirmed in Ontario (CSE).

Schoenoplectus (Chairmaker's Rush, Common Threesquare)

An unknown species of *Acalyptis* (Nepticulidae) forms a long, narrow, linear stem mine on *Schoenoplectus* (CSE). Unless it is something completely unknown to science, this threesquare stem miner appears to be *Cosmopterix scirpicola* (Cosmopterigidae),

which is not known to occur north of Maryland (Koster 2010; CSE).

DENNSTAEDTIACEAE

Pteridium aquilinum (Bracken Fern)

We found several mines like this at Coskata Woods, and they appear to be a good match for those of *Phytoliriomyza clara* (Agromyzidae), which Spencer (1969) describes as following the edge of a section of a frond. (CSE)

ERICACEAE

Arctostaphylos uva-ursi (Bearberry)

Tamalia coweni (Aphididae) causes thickened, reddish, marginal folds in bearberry leaves. (Felt 1940; CSE)

Epigaea repens (Trailing Arbutus)

Mines in trailing arbutus leaves are made by *Brachys howdeni* (Buprestidae), which was described in 2016 by Henry Hespenheide. This young mine was found in August; the larvae overwinter in their mines and adults emerge in spring. An adult that emerged on May 31 from a leaf collected on Nantucket was included in the type series (Hespenheide & Eiseman 2016). (CSE)

Gaylussacia (Huckleberry, Dangleberry)

The fungus *Exobasidium vaccinii* (Exobasidiaceae) causes leaf and bud galls on dangleberry and huckleberry in the spring. (CSE)

Leaf spots on dangleberry and huckleberry are caused by an undescribed species of *Contarinia* (Cecidomyiidae). (Gagné 1989; CSE)

This marginal leaf roll on huckleberry was caused by a gall midge (*Cecidomyiidae*), but this is the first record of such a gall on this host. Raymond J. Gagné examined a larva we obtained from a similar gall on highbush blueberry (off island) and reported that it resembled the genus *Putoniella* (CSE).

Narrow linear mines in huckleberry leaves are made by *Stigmella corylifoliella* (Nepticulidae). (Eiseman & Charney 2010; CSE)

Coptodisca magnella (Heliozelidae) makes small linear-blotch mines in huckleberry leaves. When finished feeding, the larva cuts out an oval piece of the leaf to make its pupal case, which is attached to a leaf or twig (Braun 1916). (CSE)

Lyonetia latistrigella (Lyonetiidae) makes linear-blotch mines in the young leaves of various ericaceous shrubs. This single huckleberry leaf is the only evidence we have found of this moth on Nantucket. (Braun 1912; Maier 1995; CSE)

Phyllonorycter diversella (Gracillariidae) makes underside tentiform mines on huckleberry and dangleberry. (Braun 1908; CSE)

Kalmia angustifolia (Sheep Laurel)

Coptodisca kalmiella (Heliozelidae) forms a small linear-blotch mine on sheep laurel, cutting out an oval leaf piece to construct its pupal case (JAB).

Parornix kalmiella (Gracillariidae) makes an underside tentiform mine on sheep laurel (CSE).

Larvae of *Coleophora kalmiella* (Coleophoridae) feed from portable cases, forming frass-free blotch mines that they enter through round holes in the lower epidermis (CSE).

Lyonia ligustrina (Maleberry)

An undescribed species of *Parornix* (Gracillariidae) makes an underside tentiform mine on maleberry (CSE).

The large, shining eggshell on the surface of this mine identifies it as the work of a *Brachys* species (Buprestidae). Henry Hespeneide examined the adult we reared from maleberry and determined that it belongs to an undescribed species, of which he has seen very few other specimens (CSE).

The mine of *Lyonetia latistrigella* (Lyonetiidae) is initially narrow and linear, suddenly expanding to a full-depth blotch (CSE).

Stigmella corylifoliella (Nepticulidae) is presumed to be the species responsible for linear mines on maleberry (CSE).

Rhododendron (Azalea)

Irregular, fleshy galls on azalea are caused by the fungus *Exobasidium vaccinii* (Exobasidiaceae). They appear in May. (CSE)

Linear leaf mines in azalea are the work of *Stigmella corylifoliella* (Nepticulidae). (NDC)

Larvae of *Caloptilia porphyretica* (Gracillariidae) form underside tentiform mines (left) in azalea leaves before exiting to create leaf cones (right) by rolling the leaves downward from the tip (Braun 1923). The introduced species *C. azaleella* also mines in azalea but it folds or ties together leaves rather than making the classic *Caloptilia* cone. (CSE)

Vaccinium (Blueberry, Cranberry)

Hemadas nubilipennis (Pteromalidae) causes these irregular galls on blueberry stems. Johnson (1930) attributed them to *Selenozopheria vaccinii*, a misspelling of *Solenozopheria vaccinii* (Cynipidae), which is currently *Loxaulus vaccinii*—a species that actually produces stem galls in oaks (Krombein et al. 1979; NDC)

At least two *Caloptilia* species (Gracillariidae) feed on blueberry leaves, first in an underside mine and later in a rolled leaf. This one may be *Caloptilia porphyretica*, which we found mining in azalea leaves nearby, or *C. vacciniella*, a species listed by Jones and Kimball (1943) as present on Nantucket (CSE).

Parornix preciosella (Gracillariidae) forms an underside tentiform mine on blueberry. It spins a cocoon outside the mine, without feeding in a leaf roll or fold (CSE).

Stigmella corylifoliella (Nepticulidae) forms linear mines in cranberry and blueberry leaves (CSE).

An unidentified species of *Coptodisca* (Heliozelidae) makes a small mine on highbush blueberry leaves, cutting out an oval pupal case from the finished mine. (CSE)

We found several examples of the “maple leafcutter” (Incurvariidae: *Paraclemensia acerifoliella*) feeding on blueberry leaves. The larva cuts out oval leaf pieces to form a portable shelter, leaving characteristic rings of skeletonized leaf tissue at its feeding sites (CSE).

FABACEAE

Baptisia tinctoria (Wild Indigo)

Liriomyza baptisiae (Agromyzidae) makes linear-blotch mines in wild indigo leaves. (Spencer & Steyskal 1986; CSE)

Desmodium (Tick-trefoil)

Porphyrosela desmodiella (Gracillariidae) forms underside tentiform mines in tick-trefoil leaves (CSE).

Lespedeza (Bush Clover)

Porphyrosela desmodiella (Gracillariidae) forms underside tentiform mines in bush clover leaves, often with multiple larvae in a single mine (Braun 1908). (CSE)

These folded-leaflet galls are caused by an unknown gall midge (Cecidomyiidae), possibly in the genus *Dasineura*. (CSE)

Robinia pseudoacacia (Black Locust)

In addition to the species below, Johnson (1930) lists *Agonopterix robiniella* (Elachistidae), which folds black locust leaflets lengthwise, and *Ecdyolopha insitiana* (Tortricidae), which causes swellings in black locust twigs.

Parectopa robiniella (Gracillariidae) makes a digitate mine centered on the midrib of black locust leaflets. This is the sole leaf-mining moth listed by Johnson (1930). (Eiseman & Charney 2010; NDC)

Non-digitate blotch mines on black locust are made by other gracillariids. *Chrysaster ostensackenella* makes flat, yellowish mines, usually on the upper side of the leaf but sometimes on the underside. *Macrosaccus robiniella*, which we have not found on Nantucket, makes a tentiform mine usually on the underside of the leaf, but sometimes on the upper side. Mines are flat at first and could be confused with those of *C. ostensackenella*, but they are bright white and more superficial. (De Prins & De Prins 2010; NDC)

Filatima pseudacaciella (Gelechiidae) ties together two black locust leaflets, skeletonizing the leaf tissue within this shelter. It also sometimes enters the mines of the species discussed above (Eiseman & Charney 2010, Davis & De Prins 2011; NDC).

Tephrosia virginiana (Goat's Rue)

These swollen, folded leaflet galls on goat's rue are unknown to science. Raymond J. Gagné examined larvae that emerged from them and identified them as belonging to the tribe **Lasiopteridi** (Cecidomyiidae) (CSE).

Trifolium repens (White Clover)

These folds in clover leaflets are caused by *Dasineura trifolii* (Cecidomyiidae) (CSE).

Liriomyza fricki (Agromyzidae) forms linear-blotch mines in clover leaves (CSE).

FAGACEAE

Castanea mollissima (Chinese Chestnut)

Neurobathra strigifinitella

(Gracillariidae) initially forms a linear mine on the lower leaf surface, then enters the midrib and proceeds toward the leaf apex, where it forms a blotch mine (CSE).

This blotch mine was made by a *Brachys* larva (Buprestidae), probably *B. aerosus*, which was parasitized by a eulophid wasp (CSE).

Japanagromyza viridula (Agromyzidae) mines leaves while they are still young and tender, forming irregular blotches that tear and deteriorate as the leaves mature (CSE).

Paraclemensia acerifoliella (Incurvariidae) is initially a leafminer, then spends most of its life feeding on the leaf surface from a portable case made of pieces cut out of the leaf (CSE).

Fagus grandifolia (Beech)

Acalitus ferrugineum (Eriophyidae) forms erineum patches on the lower surface of beech leaves, visible as pale green spots on the upper surface (CSE).

This feeding sign found at Masquetuck appears to be from adult *Brachys* beetles (Buprestidae), but we have yet to find any beech leaf mines on Nantucket. (CSE)

Quercus (Oak)

Rosette galls on dwarf chinquapin oak twigs are caused by *Andricus flavohirtus* (Cynipidae). (Weld 1959; NDC)

Callirhytis clavula (Cynipidae) causes terminal, clublike swellings in white oak twigs. The buds protruding from these galls are often viable. (Eiseman & Charney 2010; NDC)

This white oak twig swelling is caused by *Neuroterus quercusbatatus* (Cynipidae). (Weld 1959; CSE)

Pronounced one- to four-celled swellings on scrub oak (and other red oak group) twigs, which may or may not be terminal like the one pictured here, are caused by *Zapatella quercusphellos* (Cynipidae). The wasps overwinter in the gall, emerging in spring. (Weld 1959; NDC)

Callirhytis tuberosa (Cynipidae), listed by Johnson (1930), also forms galls in scrub oak twigs, causing a “much shortened thickened portion of the new growth . . . bearing many leaves, many-celled, up to 15 mm long by 6 mm” in diameter, appearing in June. This gall is said to be rare, and we did not find any examples. (Weld 1959; CSE)

Callirhytis quercusscitula (Cynipidae) forms terminal swellings (“abrupt enlargement of new growth bearing normal leaves”) in black and scrub oak twigs, which are fully formed in June. Adults emerge in June or July. All but one of the leaves had dropped off this one when we found it in September. (Weld 1959; NDC)

Callirhytis quercuspunctata (Cynipidae) causes multicelled, knotty, irregular swellings in twigs of the red oak group. They can be much more pronounced than the one shown here. (Weld 1959; CSE)

Zapatella davisae (Cynipidae) causes rather inconspicuous swellings in black oak twigs, but the galls have been causing substantial dieback on Nantucket in recent years. (CSE)

The **cynipid** species that forms similar galls on white oak twigs has never been reared and may be undescribed. (Kelly Omand)

“Banded bullet galls” on twigs of the red oak group are caused by *Dryocosmus imbricariae* (Cynipidae). They drop to the ground in September. (Weld 1959; CSE)

The hard “round bullet galls” on twigs of white and dwarf chinquapin oak are caused by *Disholcaspis quercusglobulus* (Cynipidae), listed by Johnson (1930) as *D. globulus*. In May, we collected some particularly large galls of this species, one of which turned out to have a colony of tiny ants living in it. An inquiline emerged from another of these in early July. (Weld 1959; NDC)

These densely clustered twig galls on dwarf chinquapin oak are labeled in Johnson's collection as *Disholcaspis pernicios* (Cynipidae). However, this is a southwestern species found on other species of oak (Krombein et al. 1979), so it is evidently misidentified. It seems to be the "oak fig gall," which is caused by *Trigonaspis quercusforticorne* (listed by

Weld [1959] as *Xystoteras forticorne*) and also occurs on white oak. (Felt 1940; CSE)

These clustered, beaked twig galls have been found on scrub oak in June, at Squam Swamp, in the Middle Moors, and at the mile marker 5 parking lot on Milestone Road. We believe they are caused by *Callirhytis quercusventricosa* (Cynipidae). So far we have only managed to rear parasitoids (Ormyridae: *Ormyrus* sp.) and a gelechiid moth from them. (Danielle O'Dell)

This "spongy oak apple" gall on scrub oak was caused by either *Amphibolips confluenta* or *A. quercusspongifica* (CSE).

This "oak apple" gall found on scrub oak is almost certainly caused by an *Amphibolips* species (Cynipidae), but it does not seem to be one of the galls described by Weld (1959). (CSE)

This speckled “oak apple” found on scrub oak seems intermediate between the previous and following galls. (NDC)

These “oak apples” found on black oak are a good match for an undescribed *Amphibolips* species illustrated by Weld (1959), also found on southern red oak. (NDC)

“Oak plum” galls, caused by *Amphibolips quercusjuglans* (Cynipidae), form on the sides of acorn caps on black and scrub oaks. They fall to the ground separately, looking like little (~1 inch) reddish apples. The flesh of the fresh galls is also apple-like. (Weld 1959; CSE)

This 3-mm **cynipid** gall on a scrub oak twig was secreting honeydew, attracting a group of acrobat ants (*Crematogaster cerasi*). We have only found references to acorn ‘pip’ galls secreting honeydew, and since this one is protruding from a bud, it is unclear what it might be. A similar gall found nearby was attached to an acorn, so this may in fact be the same species as the gall below. (CSE)

Callirhytis balanacea (Cynipidae) seems to be the best match for this tiny, honeydew-secreting gall on the side of a developing acorn. It is possible, however, that it was caused by another *Callirhytis* species. (Weld 1959; CSE)

This tiny gall on a scrub oak acorn cap was presumably caused by a gall wasp (**Cynipidae**), but we have not found any references to a gall like this in the literature. (CSE)

Callirhytis quercusoperator, listed by Johnson (1930) as *C. operator*, forms woolly galls on catkins of the red oak group in May. The alternating generation of this species causes flattened “pip” galls on mature acorns (the specimen shown is from Johnson’s collection). (Weld 1959; CSE)

The hollow, spheroid galls of *Dryocosmus quercuspalustris* (Cynipidae) are found on catkins and developing leaves of the red oak group in May. Dissection reveals a small, free-rolling cell containing the larva. (Weld 1959; CSE)

Andricus quercuspetiolicola (Cynipidae) forms conspicuous swellings in the petioles or bases of blades of leaves in the white oak group. (Weld 1959; CSE)

Swellings in midribs and petioles of the red oak group are caused by *Melikaiella tumifica* (Cynipidae). The galls are fully formed in May, and adults emerge in early summer, but the galls can still be found in September. (Weld 1959; CSE)

Large, spindle-shaped “oak apples” on scrub oak leaves are caused by *Amphibolips quercusilicifoliae* (Cynipidae), listed by Johnson (1930) as *A. ilicifoliae*. The galls form in spring but old ones can still be found in September. (Weld 1959; NDC)

These faceted galls on veins of white oak leaves are caused by *Acraspis pezomachoides* (Cynipidae). (Weld 1959; NDC)

This spiny gall on dwarf chinquapin oak leaves is caused by *Acraspis prinoides* (Cynipidae), one of the species recorded by Johnson (1930). (Weld 1959; NDC)

Philonix nigra (Cynipidae) causes spherical, felt-covered galls on leaves of the white oak group. According to Weld (1959), they occur on the underside of the leaf and range from 5-8 mm. These galls, found on dwarf chinquapin oak leaves, ranged from 4-13 mm and were more often on the upper surface (and always on the midrib), but we believe them to be caused by the same species. In October an adult cynipid emerged from a 7-8 mm gall from a leaf underside, and Matt Buffington confirmed our identification. (CSE)

Phylloteras poculum (Cynipidae) causes whitish “spangle galls” on the undersides of leaves in the white oak group. (Weld 1959; NDC)

Dryocosmus deciduus (Cynipidae) produces clusters of detachable galls that erupt from the midribs of leaves in the black oak group. Most of the galls have already fallen out in this example. (CSE)

These distinctive galls, found clustered on main veins on the upper surface of black oak leaves, are surely caused by **cynipid** wasps, but do not seem to match any described by Weld (1959). Photos of similar galls from Florida, Alabama, Maryland, and mainland Massachusetts, on willow oak and other red oaks, can be seen at <http://bugguide.net/node/view/356574>. (NDC)

The identity of these woolly galls, found on the underside of a scrub oak leaf midrib, is also uncertain, though it seems likely they are caused by a *Callirhytis* species (Cynipidae). (NDC)

This small, spherical gall, found on the underside of a dwarf chinquapin oak leaf, does not match any known cynipid galls on this host. It may have been caused by *Polystepha globosa* (Cecidomyiidae; see below). (NDC)

A cynipid inquiline emerged from this unidentified 1-mm gall on the underside of a scrub oak leaf. (CSE)

This unidentified 1-mm gall was found attached to a side vein on the underside of a scrub oak leaf. It almost certainly was caused by a cynipid. (CSE)

Small, fleshy, white, compressed spherical galls on the undersides of leaves in the red oak group are caused by *Dryocosmus albidus* (Cynipidae). (Weld 1959; NDC)

When tiny cynipids appeared in a bag containing a dwarf chinquapin oak twig that had been collected for its *Disholcaspis quercusglobulus* galls, this leaf fragment was determined to be the source. These small, fuzzy galls on the leaf underside are caused by *Neuroterus quercusverrucarum*.

Round, 2 mm blisters on white oak leaves are caused by *Neuroterus niger* (Cynipidae). (Weld 1959; CSE)

Elliptical, 1 mm blisters on white oak leaves are caused by *Neuroterus perminimus* (Cynipidae). (Weld 1959; CSE)

This gall in a vein axil on the underside of a scrub oak leaf, less than half a millimeter across, was determined to be the source of a tiny chalcid parasitoid that emerged (the leaf was collected for a *Stigmella* leaf mine). It was presumably caused by a cynipid. (CSE)

These yellow galls found along the midrib of a dwarf chinquapin oak leaf do not resemble any known cynipid galls. They are somewhat reminiscent of the galls of *Polystepha pilulae* (Cecidomyiidae) shown below, but we believe they are something else. So far only parasitoids have emerged from them. (CSE)

These irregular galls on the upper sides of leaves were by far the most abundant oak galls on Tuckernuck. They are caused by *Polystepha pilulae* (Cecidomyiidae), listed by Johnson (1930) as *Cincticornia pilulae*. (Eiseman & Charney 2010; NDC)

Polystepha globosa (Cecidomyiidae) seems to be the best match for these 2-mm spherical galls found on the underside of a scrub oak leaf. (Gagné 1989; CSE)

Several *Polystepha* species (Cecidomyiidae) produce circular, flat blister galls on oak leaves (Gagné 1989). We initially believed that was what these galls on scrub oak leaves were, but gall wasps (**Cynipidae**) emerged in the spring of 2018 from some that we had collected the previous fall. These galls do not match the description of any cynipid galls previously reported from scrub oak. (CSE)

Macrodiplosis niveipila (Cecidomyiidae) causes elongate, fuzzy folds along oak leaf veins, often deforming the leaf. There is a slitlike opening on the upper surface of the leaf, through which the larvae exit when mature. We found fresh galls in May, and larvae emerged from them on May 22-23 to burrow into soil. Adults emerged the following April. Raymond J. Gagné, to whom we sent the specimens, wrote: "The *Macrodiplosis* females you reared from oaks cannot be identified further. What further identification would require is an exclusive and at least three-year project collecting galls from all the oaks east of the Mississippi, retaining some larvae and rearing adults from each kind of gall and host. Basing *Macrodiplosis* identifications on anything less than that would just be guesswork." Therefore, this and all other

Macrodiplosis identifications presented here should be considered tentative, pending revision of the genus. (Gagné 1989; NDC)

Macrodiplosis qoruca

(Cecidomyiidae) causes elongate, smooth (not fuzzy) folds along oak leaf veins, with a slitlike opening on the upper surface of the leaf. (Gagné 1989; CSE)

Macrodiplosis majalis

(Cecidomyiidae) causes short, pea-sized pouch galls on the undersides of oak leaves, with a slitlike opening on the upper leaf surface. (Gagné 1989; NDC)

Galls on oak leaves with a slitlike opening on the upper side belong to the genus ***Macrodiplosis*** (Cecidomyiidae), as in the examples above. However, none of the species described by Gagné (1989) match these, with short, oval pouches on the underside and a pair of tapered 'lips' projecting from the upper side. These may be atypical galls of *M. majalis*, or may represent an undescribed species. (NDC)

Contarinia (Cecidomyiidae) are folds along leaf veins, forming striate bulges on the leaf underside. (Gagné 1989; CSE)

Macrodiplosis erubescens (Cecidomyiidae) larvae develop in small folds at the edges of oak leaves. (Gagné 1989; CSE)

We found gall midge (**Cecidomyiidae**) larvae in these marginal leaf rolls on dwarf chinquapin oak, but no species is known to cause galls like these.

Large blisters on oak leaves, convex above and concave below, are caused by a fungus, ***Taphrina caerulescens*** (Taphrinaceae). (Sinclair & Lyon 2005; CSE)

Contorted, narrow mines in oak bark, like this one on a gall of *Callirhytis quercussimilis*, are the work of *Zimmermannia bosquella* (Nepticulidae). (CSE)

Neurobathra strigifinitella (Gracillariidae) mines primarily in the midribs of oak leaves, sometimes expanding to a blotch mine in the leaf blade. (Heinrich & DeGryse 1915; CSE)

A number of species of *Bucculatrix* (Bucculatricidae) feed on oak. The larva forms a small linear mine, then emerges to feed in little patches on the lower leaf surface. When finished feeding, it spins a characteristic cocoon with longitudinal ridges. We found

mines and larvae of an undetermined species on scrub oak, and reared *B. trifasciella* from cocoons found on white oak. (CSE)

Several *Stigmella* species (Nepticulidae) make narrow, linear mines in oak leaves with a continuous frass trail down the middle. (Eiseman & Charney 2010; CSE)

Linear mines on leaves of black and scrub oaks that widen dramatically toward the end are characteristic of *Stigmella quercipulchella* (Nepticulidae) (CSE).

Linear leaf mines on oaks with a very broad frass trail are characteristic of *Stigmella nigriverticella* (Nepticulidae). It is possible that the similar species *S. macrocarpae* forms similar mines, but Erik van Nieukerken confirmed the identity of an adult we reared from scrub oak (NDC).

An undescribed *Ectoedemia* species (Nepticulidae) mines leaves of scrub oak in September, initially forming a narrow, highly contorted linear mine that develops into an elongate blotch. This species was first discovered in September 2011, when Erik van Nieukerken found it

at Harvard Forest at the same time we collected a larva at Squam Swamp. There were no further records of it until we found several examples at Stump Pond in September 2019. (CSE)

Underside linear-blotch mines on oak leaves are the work of *Acrocercops albinatella* (Gracillariidae) (Chambers 1877; CSE).

Coptotriche castaneaeella (Tischeriidae) makes a trumpet-shaped mine on the upper surface of an oak leaf, with characteristic concentric crescents marked in the upper epidermis. These crescents were not evident in the young mines when we collected them. (Eiseman & Charney 2010; CSE)

Coptotriche fuscomarginella (Tischeriidae) makes a trumpet mine with the excrement packed in an elongate mass in the narrower portion. It lacks the concentric crescents that *C. castaneaeella* leaves in the upper epidermis of otherwise similar mines. (Eiseman & Charney 2010; CSE)

Coptotriche citrinipennella (Tischeriidae), listed by Jones and Kimball (1943) as *Tischeria citrinipennella*, makes an elongate blotch mine along the margin of an oak leaf, causing the leaf margin to curl. (Eiseman & Charney 2010; CSE)

Coptotriche purinosella (Tischeriidae) forms small, whitish mines at the margins of white oak leaves, not typically causing the margin to curl (CSE).

The distinctive radiating purplish markings left by *Tischeria quercitella* larvae (Tischeriidae) makes their mines easy to identify even in their very early stages. (Braun 1972; CSE)

Blotch mines on oak with frass deposited on the surface are made by species of *Stilbosis* (Cosmopterigidae). (CSE)

Flat, irregular, upperside blotch mines, like these on white oak, are the work of *Cameraria* species (Gracillariidae). Thirty Nearctic species in this genus are known to feed on oak leaves, and although many can be ruled out based on geography and mine characteristics, it is not possible to identify these mines to species. (De Prins & De Prins 2010; CSE)

Three larvae can be seen mining side by side in this white oak leaf mine, and this identifies them as *Cameraria cincinnatiella*, the gregarious oak leafminer. White oak is the most common host of this species, which appears to be specific to the white oak group. (Maier & Davis 1989; JAB)

Cameraria quercivorella makes a particularly small mine, often placed at the tip of a lobe (Braun 1908; CSE).

Leaf mines of *Profenusa lucifex* (Tenthredinidae) can be distinguished from other blotch mines on oak leaves by the combination of the egg being inserted (rather than glued to the leaf surface), the frass being in scattered oblong pellets, and the larva exiting through a slit in the epidermis when finished feeding (CSE).

Brachys (Buprestidae) larvae make frass-filled blotch mines along the edges of oak leaves, and adults eat meandering channels into the leaf edges. Johnson (1930) lists *B. aerosus* as being common on Nantucket, and *B. aeruginosus* as being found on both Nantucket and Tuckernuck. We found adults of both species on Nantucket, as well as *B. ovatus*. (CSE)

Underside tentiform mines on oak leaves are made by *Phyllonorycter* species (Gracillariidae). Fifteen Nearctic species in this genus are known to feed on oak leaves, and seven of them on white oak, but of these only *P. basistrigella* pupates in a flat oval cocoon with a narrow outline of droppings, as the larva that made the mine on the left did after we collected it. Similar leafminers in scrub oak and white oak leaves made rounded cocoons

entirely covered with droppings (right photo), revealing themselves to be *P. aeriferella*. (Eiseman & Charney 2010; CSE)

Phyllonorycter rileyella (Gracillariidae) deposits its frass at one end of its mine, pupates in a slight web, and emerges from the opposite end of the mine (CSE).

Larvae of oak shothole leafminers (Agromyzidae: *Japanagromyza viridula*) are active in early June, forming blotch mines that disfigure young, developing oak leaves. In addition to laying

eggs, adult females use their ovipositors to make additional feeding punctures, which become large, irregular holes when the leaves are fully expanded. (Labonte & Lipovsky 1967; CSE, NDC)

Eriocraniella platyptera (Eriocraniidae) is also only active in the spring, and like *J. viridula* the oviposition puncture is stretched out as the leaf expands. The larva makes a narrow linear mine that abruptly expands to a full-depth blotch with distinctively coiled, stringy excrement inside. This moth's immature stages had not been documented prior to this survey. (Eiseman 2016; CSE)

A likely undescribed species of *Coptodisca* (Heliozelidae) forms a tiny mine in scrub oak leaves, then cuts out an oval section of the mine to use as a pupal case. (CSE)

Povolnya quercinigrella (Gracillariidae) is initially a leafminer, later tying down a leaf lobe and skeletonizing the tissue within and adjacent to it (CSE).

These distinctive underside pseudo-mines on scrub oak are the work of *Menesta melanella* (Elachistidae). When mature, the larvae cut out large oval leaf pieces in which to pupate. (Murtfeldt 1890; NDC)

Catastega timidella (Tortricidae) lives inside a tube of its own excrement on the underside of an oak leaf, further protected by webbing, and feeds on the tissue on the leaf underside. (Eiseman & Charney 2010; CSE)

We found larvae of the “maple leafcutter” (Incurvariidae: *Paraclemensia acerifoliella*) feeding on leaves of scrub oak and post oak. The larva cuts out oval leaf pieces to form a portable shelter, leaving characteristic rings of skeletonized leaf tissue at its feeding sites (CSE).

HAMAMELIDACEAE

Hamamelis virginiana (Witch Hazel)

Kelly Omand found galls like these on the recently discovered witch hazel plants in Coskata Woods. They are caused by *Hamamelistes spinosus* (Aphididae). (CSE)

HYPERICACEAE

Hypericum adpressum (Creeping St. Johnswort)

Caloptilia hypericella (Gracillariidae) is initially a leafminer and later a leafroller on various St. Johnswort species. This adult emerged from some rolled leaves that we collected in an attempt to rear another, still unidentified leafroller. (CSE)

Triadenum virginicum (Marsh St. Johnswort)

Fomoria hypericella (Nepticulidae) forms a linear-blotch mine in St. Johnswort leaves (CSE).

IRIDACEAE

Iris versicolor (Blue Flag)

From this iris leaf mine we reared the only known specimen of *Cerodontha edithae* (Agromyzidae), named in honor of Edith Andrews (Eiseman & Lonsdale 2018; CSE).

A closely related species, *Cerodontha thompsoni* (Agromyzidae), forms a zigzagging linear mine that descends to the very base of the plant. When the mine is in the youngest, innermost leaf, a gall forms around the fly's puparium the following spring. This species was listed by Johnson (1930) as *Agromyza laterella* (CSE).

Sisyrinchium fuscatum (Sandplain Blue-eyed Grass)

We reared a probably undescribed species of *Marmara* (Gracillariidae) from these leaf mines on sandplain blue-eyed grass (CSE).

JUGLANDACEAE

Carya tomentosa (Mockernut Hickory)

This hickory leaf gall is caused by a species of *Phylloxera* (Phylloxeridae). (CSE)

These are partially formed galls of the “hickory bullet gall midge,” *Caryomyia tubicola* (Cecidomyiidae) (CSE).

Gliaspilota glutinosa (Cecidomyiidae) feeds on the lower surface of hickory leaves, causing an often ring-shaped welt to form (CSE).

Coptodisca lucifluella (Heliozelidae) forms a small linear-blotch mine in hickory leaves, cutting out an oval pupal case when mature (CSE).

The pale green larva of *Ectoedemia virgulae* (Nepticulidae) forms a larger linear-blotch mine, exiting through a slit in the leaf epidermis when ready to spin its cocoon (CSE).

Stigmella caryaefoliella (Nepticulidae) forms an entirely linear mine with frass in a narrow central line (CSE).

JUNCACEAE

Juncus canadensis (Canada Rush), *J. effusus* (Soft Rush), *J. tenuis* (Path Rush)

Livia bifasciata (Liviidae; listed by Johnson [1930] as *Livia maculipennis* under Chermidae) causes galls in Canada Rush inflorescences. The flower parts are aborted, and there is a dense growth of oversized bracts, 3-4 cm long (Weiss & West 1922; Hodkinson & Bird 2000; CSE).

Larvae of the sawfly *Eutomostethus luteiventris* (Tenthredinidae) mine and bore in rush stems, eventually causing them to flop over (CSE).

A collection of leaf mines in the narrow leaves of path rush produced adults of *Cerodontha angulata* as well as a female of what appears to be *C.*

incisa (Agromyzidae). The latter species is otherwise only known to feed on grasses (Eiseman & Lonsdale 2018; CSE).

LAMIACEAE

Lycopus uniflorus (Northern Bugleweed)

Neolasioptera lycopi (Cecidomyiidae) forms galls in bugleweed stems (Kelly Omand).

Mentha spicata (Spearmint)

Calycomyza menthae (Agromyzidae) forms linear-blotch mines in mint leaves (CSE).

Teucrium canadense (American germander)

Nemorimyza posticata (Agromyzidae), a fly normally associated with Asteraceae, also mines leaves of American germander (Eiseman & Lonsdale 2018; CSE).

Trichostema (Bluecurls)

Stigmatophora sexnotella (Cosmopterigidae), listed by Jones & Kimball (1943), causes stem galls on bluecurls.

LAURACEAE

Sassafras albidum (Sassafras)

Eugnamptus angustatus (Attelabidae), listed by Johnson (1930), mines dead leaves of sassafras and other trees in the leaf litter.

Leaf spots on sassafras are caused by an undescribed *Contarinia* species (Cecidomyiidae). (Gagné 1989; CSE)

Caloptilia sassafrasella (Gracillariidae) forms a small underside blotch mine, then exits and feeds in a leaf roll (CSE).

MAGNOLIACEAE

Liriodendron tulipifera (Tulip Tree)

Phyllocnistis liriodendronella (Gracillariidae) makes long, narrow mines on either the upper or lower surface of tulip tree leaves.

Resseliella liriodendri (Cecidomyiidae) causes leaf spot galls. (Eiseman & Charney 2010, Gagné 1989; NDC)

MALVACEAE

Hibiscus moscheutos (Swamp Rose-mallow)

The leaf mine of *Telamoptilia hibiscivora* (Gracillariidae) begins as an epidermal track on the lower leaf surface, then forms an interparenchymal blotch, which ultimately becomes more or less full-depth (CSE).

Tilia americana (Basswood)

Stigmella argentifasciella (Nepticulidae) forms linear-blotch mines in basswood leaves. (CSE)

MYRICACEAE

Comptonia peregrina (Sweetfern)

Aspilanta argentifera (Heliozelidae) mines in sweetfern leaves, cutting out an oval pupal case when mature (CSE).

This case-bearing leafminer is one of several species of sweetfern-feeding *Coleophora* species (Coleophoridae). (Bucheli et al. 2002; CSE)

Parornix peregrinaella (Gracillariidae) feeds in the tip of a sweetfern leaf, curling it into a tight tube, then exits and pupates under a folded-down pinnule (CSE).

Morella caroliniensis (Bayberry)

Coleophora comptoniella (Coleophoridae) lives in a portable case, from which it extends the front of its body to mine into bayberry leaves. The photo at right shows the small abandoned case of a young larva next to the area where the larva

cut its new, larger case out from the leaf margin (CSE).

DNA barcoding has confirmed that the larva pictured here is *Stigmella myricafoliella* (Nepticulidae), which was previously only known from Florida. Other linear mines on bayberry have been attributed to *S. ostryaefoliella* in the past (Newton & Wilkinson 1982), but Erik J. van Nieuwerkerken reports that all other DNA sequences he has seen from bayberry-mining larvae were *S. corylifoliella*. He suspects that references to *S. ostryaefoliella* mining in bayberry represent misidentifications. (CSE)

Brownish blotch mines on the upper sides of bayberry leaves are made by *Cameraria picturatella* (Gracillariidae), listed in Jones & Kimball (1943) as *Lithocolletis picturatella*. (De Prins & De Prins 2010; NDC)

We collected these linear-blotch mines in June, before any *Stigmella* or *Cameraria* larvae were active in bayberry leaves, and reared several adults of an undescribed moth. According to David Wagner, it belongs to an undescribed genus in the subfamily **Ornixolinae** (Gracillariidae). (CSE)

Aspilanta argentifera (Heliozelidae) mines in bayberry leaves, cutting out an oval pupal case when it is done feeding (CSE).

NYMPHAEACEAE

Nymphaea (Waterlily)

Bagous americanus (Curculionidae), listed by Johnson (1930), mines leaves of waterlilies.

NYSSACEAE

Nyssa sylvatica (Tupelo)

The curling along the edge of this tupelo leaf is caused by a mite, *Aceria dina* (Eriophyidae) (CSE).

These smoother tupelo leaf edge curls are caused by an aphidlike insect, *Phylloxera nyssae* (Phylloxeridae). (Gagné 1989; CSE)

Antispila nysaefoliella
(Heliozelidae) makes small, rapidly widening mines in tupelo leaves. When finished feeding, the larva cuts out an oval leaf piece, in which it pupates, attached to some object away from the mine. (Eiseman & Charney 2010; NDC)

The larva of ***Ectoedemia nysaefoliella*** (Nepticulidae) starts out making a long, narrow, contorted, linear mine with a dark trail of excrement down the center. This widens gradually and ends in a large, amorphous blotch. (Eiseman & Charney 2010; NDC)

This tupelo bark mine was likely made by an undescribed species of ***Marmara*** (Gracillariidae). (CSE)

OLEACEAE

Fraxinus (Ash)

Kelly Omand found galls like these on male flowers of an ash tree growing at Mill Hill Park. They are caused by a mite, *Aceria fraxiniflora* (Eriophyidae). (CSE)

Ligustrum (Privet)

Larvae of *Gracillaria syringella* (Gracillariidae) mine in the undersides of leaves of privet, lilac, and related plants, later exiting to form a leaf roll as in *Caloptilia* species. Jones & Kimball (1943) reported that this species was rare on Nantucket, and that still appears to be the case—we found signs of this species on a single bush after examining many privet hedgerows. (Ellis 2013; CSE)

OROBANCHACEAE

Melampyrum lineare (Cow-wheat)

Linear-blotch mines on cow-wheat are made by *Liriomyza pistilla* (Agromyzidae), a species described in 2017. Specimens from Masquetuck were used in the description and are part of the type series (CSE).

OSMUNDACEAE

Osmundastrum cinnamomeum (Cinnamon Fern)

We reared *Chirosia filicis* (Anthomyiidae) from leaf mines like this one at Squam Swamp (Eiseman 2018). (CSE)

PINACEAE

Picea abies (Norway Spruce)

Adelges abietis (Adelgidae; listed by Johnson (1930) under Phylloxeridae) causes nonterminal, pineapple-like galls on spruce twigs (Eiseman & Charney 2010) (CSE).

Pinus (Pine)

Masses of resin on pitch pine twigs are formed by groups of *Cecidomyia resinicola* larvae (Cecidomyiidae). Johnson (1930) lists this species as *Retinodiplosis resinicola*. Jones & Kimball (1943) listed two tortricid moths that initially mine in pine needles, later tying them together: *Argyrotaenia pinatubana* and *Taniva albolineana*.

This pitch pine needle mine was made by *Exoteleia pinifoliella* (Gelechiidae). Each larva of this moth species mines three or more needles in its lifetime. (Freeman 1960; CSE)

This bark mine on a white pine branch is the work of *Marmara fasciella* (Gracillariidae). (De Gryse 1943; CSE)

PLANTAGINACEAE

Plantago (Plantain)

Phytomyza plantaginis (Agromyzidae) larvae form long, narrow, white mines in plantain leaves, pupating at the end of the mine. (Spencer & Steyskal 1986; CSE).

Of the known leaf mines on plantain, this one most resembles that of *Liriomyza blechi* (Agromyzidae). (CSE)

Veronica (Speedwell)

Mines of *Phytomyza crassiseta* (Agromyzidae) were found on herbarium specimens of both germander speedwell and common speedwell (JAB).

PLUMBAGINACEAE

Limonium carolinianum (Sea Lavender)

Gynnidomorpha romonana (Tortricidae) mines in sea lavender leaves. This moth's immature stages were unknown until we reared an adult from similar mines found along the Maine coast (Eiseman & Jensen 2015; CSE).

POACEAE

Johnson (1930) lists *Agromyza parvicornis* (Agromyzidae), which is known as the corn blotch leafminer. The larva of this species forms a linear blotch mine in leaves of corn and other grasses. Johnson also lists *A. coquilletti* and *Cerodontha femoralis*, both of which seem to refer to species of *Cerodontha* (but not *C. femoralis*, which is not known to occur in North America) that mine in wheat and other grasses.

Anthoxanthum odoratum (Sweet Vernal Grass)

This larva is a species of *Liriomyza* (Agromyzidae). It is distinguishable from other grass miners by the linear mine with frass in alternating strips, and by the yellow puparium it formed after exiting the mine.

Calamagrostis (Reed Grass)

This leaf mine was made by an unknown species of *Agromyzidae*. (CSE)

Dactylis glomerata (Orchard Grass)

This leaf mine was made by two larvae of *Cerodontha (Poemyza)* (Agromyzidae), probably *C. incisa*. The metallic black puparia are formed within the mine (CSE).

Dichanthelium (Rosette-panicgrass)

Several species of *Agromyza* (Agromyzidae) form similar leaf mines on *Dichanthelium* (CSE).

This mine on *Dichanthelium* was made by a different agromyzid fly, likely *Cerodontha angulata* (CSE).

Glyceria septentrionalis (Eastern Manna Grass)

The linear leaf mine of *Cerodontha dorsalis* (Agromyzidae) leads into the sheath, where pupation ultimately takes place (CSE).

This blotch mine is the work of another *Cerodontha* species, likely *C. incisa* (CSE).

Holcus lanatus (Common Velvet Grass)

The larva mining this velvet grass leaf belongs to a species of *Elachista* (Elachistidae). (CSE)

Phalaris arundinacea (Reed Canary Grass)

The linear leaf mine of *Cerodontha dorsalis* (Agromyzidae) leads into the sheath, where pupation ultimately takes place (CSE).

Phragmites (Reed)

These mines on the lower surface of both native and nonnative phragmites are made by an unknown species of *Elachista* (Elachistidae). They have been found abundantly at Sesachacha Pond and Lily Pond Park.

Spartina (Cordgrass)

No *Elachista* species is known to mine leaves of cordgrass, but we found larvae in leaves of both *S. patens* and *S. pectinata*.

POLYGONACEAE

Mantura floridana (Chrysomelidae), listed by Johnson (1930), mines leaves of *Rumex* and a few other genera in this family.

Rumex (Bitter Dock, Curly Dock, Sheep Sorrel)

Several *Pegomya* species (Anthomyiidae) form large blotch mines in dock leaves, with several larvae per mine. Johnson (1930) lists *P. bicolor* and *P. winthemi* as occurring on Nantucket. Both of these names at that time referred to species that mine bitter dock as well as curly dock (*R. crispus*) (Needham et al. 1928); however, both identifications are questionable, and the latter species is actually a mushroom feeder (Griffiths 1982, 1983; NDC)

PORTULACACEAE

Portulaca oleracea (Purslane)

Mines in purslane leaves with conspicuous excrement are the work of the only leaf-mining argid sawfly, *Schizocerella pilicornis*. In the upper right corner of this photo, the larva can be seen entering a new leaf. (Eiseman & Charney 2010; CSE)

The white larva in this leaf mine is *Pegomya rufescens*, the only anthomyiid fly that has been reared from purslane (Griffiths 1982). Like *Schizocerella pilicornis*, larvae of this species are able to exit their mines and enter new leaves. (CSE)

RANUNCULACEAE

Anemone quinquefolia (Wood Anemone)

Pseudodineura parva (Tenthredinidae) makes full-depth blotch mines in wood anemone. Ultimately the entire leaflet may be mined out. The larvae have the unusual ability (among sawflies) to exit their mines and enter new leaves. When finished feeding, the larvae burrow into the ground to overwinter. (CSE)

We reared *Phytomyza multifida* (Agromyzidae) from these linear mines in wood anemone leaves. This species was previously known only from Alberta, on a different species of *Anemone*. (CSE)

Aquilegia vulgaris (Garden Columbine)

This linear mine on a columbine leaf is made by *Phytomyza aquilegiovora* (Agromyzidae). The blotch mines are the work of *P. aquilegiana*. (Spencer & Steyskal 1986; CSE)

Ranunculus (Buttercup)

Phytomyza ranunculi (Agromyzidae) forms linear mines in buttercup leaves. (CSE)

ROSACEAE

Amelanchier (Shadbush)

These leaf galls are caused by *Blaesodiplosis canadensis* (Cecidomyiidae), listed by Johnson (1930) as *Hormomyia canadensis*. (Gagné 1989; CSE)

At least one *Parornix* species (*Gracillariidae*) forms an underside tentiform mine on shadbush, then exits and completes its development in a folded-over leaf edge (CSE).

The white object (lower left) is a larva of *Bucculatrix pomifoliella* (Bucculatricidae) in its molting cocoon. The larva initially fed as a leafminer and has now switched to eating small patches of tissue on the leaf surface (upper left; CSE).

Aronia (Chokeberry)

Parornix quadripunctella (Gracillariidae) feeds on chokeberry and has the same habits as the species on shadbush noted above (CSE).

An unidentified species of *Coptotriche* (Tischeriidae) makes an upper surface blotch on chokeberry, causing the leaf edge to curl (CSE).

The larva of *Bucculatrix pomifoliella* (Bucculatricidae) forms a short linear leaf mine, then exits to feed in small patches on the surface. (CSE)

An undescribed species of *Stigmella* (Nepticulidae) makes a much longer linear mine, completing development within it and then exiting when ready to spin its cocoon.

Crataegus (Hawthorn)

The larva forming this linear mine in a hawthorn leaf was identified as *Stigmella crataegifoliella* (Nepticulidae) by Erik van Nieukerken through DNA barcoding (CSE).

Several species of *Parornix* (Gracillariidae) feed on hawthorn, first in an underside tentiform mine and later in a folded-down leaf edge (CSE).

Geum canadense (White Avens)

The introduced European species *Metallus lanceolatus* (Tenthredinidae) is the only sawfly in North America known to mine in avens leaves. (Smith 1971; CSE)

Fragaria virginiana (Wild Strawberry)

Coleophora rupestris (Coleophoridae) mines strawberry leaves from a portable leaf case. (Bucheli et al. 2002; CSE)

Malus (Crabapple)

The green larvae of *Stigmella oxyacanthella* (Nepticulidae) form long, narrow, linear mines on apple leaves beginning in September (CSE).

The leaf mine of *Callisto denticulella* (Gracillariidae) is formed on the upper or lower surface of apple leaves. The larva exits its mine and feeds in a downward-folded leaf margin before completing its development (CSE).

In addition to *Callisto denticulella*, two species of *Parornix* (Gracillariidae) feed in underside tentiform mines on apple leaves, then exit to feed in a leaf flap (CSE).

Potentilla (Cinquefoil)

This stem swelling on dwarf cinquefoil is presumably a gall of *Neolasioptera potentillaecaulis* (Cecidomyiidae), a species Stebbins (1909) described based solely on the gall, and for which there are no known specimens of adults or larvae (CSE).

This blotch mine on a cinquefoil leaflet (left) was made by a *Coleophora rupestrella* (Coleophoridae) larva feeding on the underside from the shelter of its portable case of silk and leaf pieces (right). The leaf mine was found in May and the adult moth emerged in early July. (Bucheli et al. 2002; CSE)

This linear-blotch mine was made by an *Agromyza* species (Agromyzidae), likely *A. idaeiana* (CSE).

Prunus (Cherry, Plum)

“Black knot” galls on twigs are caused by the fungus *Dibotryon morbosum* (Venturiaceae). (CSE)

Fingerlike galls with flared-out ends on black cherry leaves are caused by *Eriophyes cerasicrumena* (Eriophyidae). They appear in May and are still evident in September. (Keifer et al. 1982; CSE)

Eriophyes emarginatae (Eriophyidae) causes fingerlike galls that do not flare out as those of *E. cerasicrumena* do, on various plums and cherries. (Keifer et al. 1982; NDC)

Swollen black cherry terminal buds are galls of *Contarinia cerasiserotinae* (Cecidomyiidae). Leaves beyond the swelling usually die, and multiple branches may later appear below the base of the gall (Gagné 1989). Larvae emerged from this gall on May 26 to burrow into soil. (CSE)

The small mine of *Coptodisca splendoriferella* begins as a narrow trail near the leaf midrib, rapidly widening to a small blotch. When done feeding, the larva cuts out an oval leaf piece, which it uses as a pupal case. (Eiseman & Charney 2010; CSE)

The mine of *Stigmella slingerlandella* (Nepticulidae) begins with a narrow linear portion with a continuous central frass line and terminates in a distinct blotch. (Eiseman & Charney 2010; NDC)

The mine of *Stigmella prunifoliella* (Nepticulidae) remains linear throughout its development. We reared adults from all four of the larvae shown in this photo. (Eiseman & Charney 2010; CSE)

We have reared *Caloptilia serotinella* (Gracillariidae) from white upperside mines like this one on cherry leaves (CSE).

We reared an adult of *Phyllonorycter propinquinella* (Gracillariidae) from this underside tentiform mine on black cherry. (CSE)

We reared *Parornix geminatella* (Gracillariidae) from beach plum, a host not previously recorded for any *Parornix*. The larva makes an underside tentiform mine, then exits to feed in a flap at the edge of the leaf. (CSE)

Orchestes pallicornis (Curculionidae), the “apple flea weevil,” was listed by Johnson (1930). The larvae are active in spring, forming puffy, full-depth mines in leaves of *Crataegus*, *Prunus*, *Malus*, and likely *Amelanchier* (Anderson 1989). The mines we found were in beach plum and black cherry, both of which are new larval host records for this species. The pictured cherry leaf is backlit to show the three circular cocoons inside. All three adult weevils emerged in late June. (CSE)

This view of the underside of a beach plum leaf shows the circular holes where this casebearer (Coleophoridae) larva entered the leaf to feed. The species is apparently *Coleophora umbratica*, the only spatulate leaf casebearer on *Prunus* listed by Bucheli et al. (2002). Braun (1914) reared *C. umbratica* from wild red plum (*P. americana*), noting that the larvae cut their cases from the leaf edge as this one has done. (CSE)

This black cherry sapling has crisscrossing bark mines of *Marmara serotinella* (Gracillariidae). (CSE)

Rosa (Rose)

These spherical, spiny galls on rose leaves are caused by *Diplolepis bicolor* (Cynipidae), listed in Johnson (1930) as *Rhodites bicolor*. (Weld 1959; CSE) A single, smaller gall we found on the upper side of a leaf in June may have been either an immature *D. bicolor* gall or possibly the gall of *D. pustulatoides*.

Diplolepis spinosa (Cynipidae) causes large, spiny galls on *Rosa rugosa* stems. (Weld 1959; CSE)

An as yet unidentified species of *Diplolepis* (Cynipidae) causes smooth galls on swamp rose stems. It may be *Diplolepis dichlocera*, listed by Johnson (1930) as *Rhodites dichlocerus*,

the species to which the preserved galls at left are attributed.

These small blisters on rose leaflets are caused by *Diplolepis rosaefolii* (Cynipidae). (Weld 1959; NDC)

We reared a species of *Contarinia* (Cecidomyiidae) from these folded-leaflet galls on roses. (CSE)

DNA barcoding revealed that these larvae mining *Rosa rugosa* leaves are the European species *Stigmella centifoliella*, which has not been documented in the US previously. (CSE)

Agromyza idaeiana (Agromyzidae) makes linear-blotch mines in rose leaflets in June. (Ellis 2014; CSE)

At least two species of *Coleophora* (Coleophoridae) make blotch mines in rose leaflets, feeding from portable cases. We reared an adult of *Coleophora rosacella* from the larva pictured here. (CSE)

Rubus (Blackberry, Dewberry, Raspberry)

Johnson (1930) lists *Trioza tripunctata* (Trioziidae; listed under Chermidae) and mentions that the “nymph lives on the under side of the terminal leaves of the blackberry, causing them to curl and form rosette-like bunches.” The dense masses of white, woolly wax produced by the nymphs covers the undersides of the leaves, distinguishing these pseudogalls from similar ones in *Rubus* leaves produced by aphids. Johnson also lists *Agrilus ruficollis* (Buprestidae), which causes swellings in raspberry stems. Although not a gallmaker, *Oberea perspicillata* (Cerambycidae; listed by Johnson as *O. bimaculata*) causes distinctive damage to raspberry

stems, making the top droop above the point where it girdles the stem to protect the egg it has inserted.

These lumpy, irregular dewberry stem galls are caused by a *Diastrophus* species (Cynipidae). (Weld 1959; CSE)

This blackberry stem swelling is caused by *Neolasioptera nodulosa* (Cecidomyiidae). The midge's pupal exuvia can be seen projecting from the gall in the upper right. (Gagné 1989; CSE)

The sawfly *Metallus rohweri* (Tenthredinidae) mines in leaves of blackberry and dewberry (Smith 1971). Johnson (1930) listed this species as *M. rubi*. (CSE)

This wrinkled upperside blotch mine on dewberry is the work of *Coptotriche aenea* (Tischeriidae). Terry Harrison examined the adult that emerged and confirmed this identification. (Braun 1972; CSE)

Ectoedemia rubifoliella (Nepticulidae) forms linear-blotch mines on dewberry (Wilkinson & Newton 1981; CSE).

Linear mines in *Rubus* species with a continuous central frass line are made by *Stigmella villosella* (Nepticulidae). (Newton & Wilkinson 1982; CSE)

Other linear mines, with frass deposited in discrete grains, are made by *Agromyza vockerothi* (Agromyzidae). The identity of this fly was a long-standing mystery (Spencer 1969; Spencer & Steyskal 1986) until we reared an adult from a mine collected at the NCF bird sanctuary in June 2012 (Eiseman & Lonsdale 2018). (NDC)

RUBIACEAE

Cephalanthus occidentalis (Buttonbush)

Mompha solomoni (Momphidae) makes both linear and blotch mines, which are often not connected to each other, on buttonbush leaves. We reared several adults from these mines, which may be difficult to distinguish from those of a close relative, *M. cephalonhiella*. Early spring generations of *M. solomoni* bore in shoots of their host plant instead of mining leaves. (Wagner et al. 2004; CSE)

SALICACEAE

Populus (Aspen, Poplar)

Johnson (1930) lists *Pemphigus populicaulis* (Aphididae), which causes a twisted, oval gall where a poplar petiole meets the leaf blade. The gall has an oblique slit that opens when the adult aphids are ready to emerge (Eiseman & Charney 2010). Johnson also lists *Agromyza aeneiventris* (Agromyzidae), which is not a valid North American species. Stebbins (1909) mentioned that oval stem swellings in quaking aspen twigs, about 8 mm long, had been attributed to this species. The species that causes these galls is now known as *Hexomyza schineri* (Eiseman & Charney 2010).

This small mine on a bigtooth aspen leaf was made by *Stigmella populetorum* (Nepticulidae). (CSE)

The introduced weevil *Isochnus sequensi* (Curculionidae) forms an upper surface mine on aspen leaves, with frass in a tarlike film on the floor of the mine. (CSE)

We reared an as yet undetermined species of *Agromyza* (Agromyzidae) from leaf mines on white poplar (CSE).

Another agromyzid fly forms more or less linear mines on bigtooth aspen leaves, often on the lower surface. We believe it to be *Aulagomyza populicola* (CSE).

The larva of *Caloptilia stigmatella* (Gracillariidae) forms an underside tentiform mine on aspen leaves, then exits to feed in a leaf roll. (CSE)

Larvae of *Zeugophora consanguinea* (Megalopodidae) form blackish blotch mines in leaves of willows and poplars. This adult was found resting on a white poplar leaf (CSE).

Although we have not yet encountered this species on Nantucket, we found this mine of *Phyllocnistis populiella* (Gracillariidae) in a pressed balm-of-Gilead leaf in the Maria Mitchell herbarium, collected by Dr. John W. Harshberger on August 22, 1913, at an unspecified location on Nantucket. (CSE)

Salix (Willow)

Johnson (1930) listed *Pontania pomum* (Tenthredinidae; now *Pontania salicispomum*), which causes round red galls on willow leaves. We found leaf galls of an undetermined *Pontania* species on two different willows, one or both of which might have been caused by *P. salicispomum*. (CSE)

These stem galls on dwarf prairie willow resemble those of *Euhexomyza* species (Agromyzidae), but some midges and sawflies also cause swellings in willow stems. Nothing emerged from the ones we collected. (CSE)

When we collected these two galls on basket willow in September, there was no external indication that they were different. However, in the spring, midges in the genus *Rabdophaga* (Cecidomyiidae) emerged from the upper gall, leaving their pupal exuviae protruding, and a sawfly in the genus *Euura* (Tenthredinidae) emerged from the lower gall, chewing a circular exit hole (CSE).

These galls on willow midribs, petioles, and stems are made by an unidentified gall midge (Cecidomyiidae). (CSE)

We reared adults of *Isochnus sequensi* (Curculionidae) from these mines on willow leaves. (CSE)

This photo shows the underside leaf mine and subsequent leaf roll of a larva of *Caloptilia stigmatella* (Gracillariidae). (CSE)

Willow stem mines are the work of *Marmara salictella* (Gracillariidae). (CSE)

SAPINDACEAE

Acer rubrum (Red Maple)

Acericecis ocellaris larvae (Cecidomyiidae) feed in small depressions on the undersides of maple leaves, causing flat, circular, discolored areas around the feeding sites. (Eiseman & Charney 2010; CSE)

At this early stage, it is not possible to tell which of the two eastern maple-feeding *Cameraria* species (Gracillariidae) is responsible for this mine. After we collected it, the mine became an elongate tract and the larva spun a cocoon in which to pupate, indicating *Cameraria aceriella* (Braun 1908; CSE).

Three eastern *Phyllonorycter* species (Gracillariidae) form underside tentiform mines in maple leaves. We have not yet determined which one is on Nantucket (CSE).

Any of four maple-feeding *Caloptilia* species (Gracillariidae) could have been responsible for this leaf cone. (De Prins & De Prins 2010; CSE)

The maple trumpet skeletonizer (Tortricidae: *Catastega aceriella*) lives inside a tube of its own excrement on the underside of a maple leaf, further protected by webbing that crumples the leaf, and feeds on the tissue on the leaf underside. (Eiseman & Charney 2010; CSE)

SMILACACEAE

Smilax (Greenbrier)

Reddened, marginal rolls in greenbrier leaves are caused by *Dasineura smilacifolia* (Cecidomyiidae). (Gagné 1989; CSE)

These very common leaf spots are caused by an undescribed gall midge species (Cecidomyiidae). Johnson (1930) attributed them to *Camptoneuromyia rubifolia*, but that species is probably a secondary inhabitant (Gagné 1989). Raymond J. Gagné (pers. comm.) has reared a *Meunieriella* species from these galls. (NDC)

Proleucoptera smilaciella (Lyonetiidae) produces messy, brown blotch mines on the upper sides of greenbrier leaves, often with up to five larvae in the same mine. (Eiseman & Charney 2010; NDC)

SOLANACEAE

Solanum carolinense (Horsenettle)

Keiferia inconspicua (Gelechiidae) forms brown, crumpling blotch mines in the margins of horsenettle leaves (CSE).

ULMACEAE

Ulmus (Elm)

Johnson (1930) lists *Eriosoma americanum* (Aphididae), which rolls the edges of elm leaves downward in early spring (Blackman and Eastop 2011).

These pronounced pouches on elm leaves are produced by a species of *Tetraneura* (Aphididae). (Eiseman & Charney 2010; NDC)

Jones & Kimball (1943) list *Coleophora limosipenella* (Coleophoridae) as being abundant on planted elms in downtown Nantucket. The larvae live in portable cases, from which they extend the front portions of their bodies to mine the leaves, forming frass-free blotch mines. The mines shown at left were made by *Coleophora* larvae, but we did not find the larvae themselves, and *C. limosipenella* is not the only elm-feeding species.

The introduced sawfly *Fenus ulmi* (Tenthredinidae) feeds on elm leaves, forming full-depth blotch mines with scattered frass (CSE).

Agromyza aristata (Agromyzidae) mines elm leaves in spring. The linear mine almost always starts at the leaf margin, and it may become more or less blotchy toward the end (CSE).

VITACEAE

Parthenocissus quinquefolia (Virginia Creeper)

Vein swellings on the undersides of Virginia creeper leaves are caused by *Dasineura parthenocissi* (Cecidomyiidae). (CSE)

These linear-blotch mines are the work of *Aspilanta ampelopsifoliella* (Heliozelidae). The mature larva cuts out an oval leaf piece to construct its pupal case (CSE).

Phyllocnistis ampelopsiella (Gracillariidae) forms contorted linear mines on the undersides of Virginia creeper leaves. (CSE)

Vitis labrusca (Fox Grape)

Deciduous, spine-shaped galls on grape leaves are caused by *Schizomyia viticola* (Cecidomyiidae), listed by Johnson (1930) as *Cecidomyia viticola*. (Gagné 1989; CSE)

Vitisiella brevicauda (Cecidomyiidae) causes irregular, succulent swellings on grape leaves and tendrils. Johnson (1930) lists only *Lasioptera vitis*, which is now believed to be a secondary inhabitant of these galls. (Gagné 1989; CSE)

Other simple spot and blister galls on grape leaves are caused by undescribed *Vitisiella* species (Cecidomyiidae). (Gagné pers. comm; CSE) We found several different types:

Upperside blisters, flat on underside (possibly a less developed version of the next type)

Smooth and convex on both sides; sometimes a pronounced globular wart on the underside

Smooth and convex above; fuzzy on underside (Tuckernuck; we reared adults from these)

Similar to (and possibly a more developed version of) the previous type, but with a tuft of fuzz on the top as well (Nantucket and Tuckernuck; we reared a pteromalid wasp from these, along with the type specimen of *Platygaster vitisiellae* (Platygastridae) (Buhl & Eiseman 2016))

Leaf spots (flat)

Heliozela aesella (Heliozelidae) makes lumpy, irregular galls on grape leaves. When finished feeding, the larva cuts out a piece of the gall to make its pupal case, as is done by its leaf-mining relatives in the genera *Antispila* and *Aspilanta*. *H. aesella* sometimes cuts a hole all the way through the leaf, but more often it is only on the upper surface of the gall. (Eiseman & Charney 2010; CSE)

Aspilanta oinophylla (left) and *Antispila isabella* (right) (Heliozelidae) form similar blotch mines in grape leaves, but the latter makes a larger mine with a correspondingly larger, and usually rounder, hole from which the pupal case is cut out (CSE).

The mine of *Phyllocnistis vitegenella* is very superficial, and the mature larva pupates in a small fold at the edge of the leaf. This distinguishes it from the mine of *P. vitifoliella*, which is deeper and whiter, with a conspicuous line of excrement, and the larva pupates in an enlargement at the end of the mine that is typically not right at the edge of the leaf (Eiseman & Charney 2010; CSE).